

The strategy of human management in providing quality teachers

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ABSTRACT

The educational goals to be achieved include all aspects, both faith, personality, intelligence, and skills. Education seeks to create a superior personality marked by progress in all areas of life, whether spiritual, personality, intelligence, or skills, all of which will benefit students, the environment in which they interact, and also for the progress of the nation and state. This research was conducted using a qualitative descriptive approach. Sugiyono explained the characteristics of qualitative research methods as follows: "Qualitative research methods are research methods based on the philosophy of postpositivism, used to examine the condition of natural objects (as opposed to experiments), where the researcher is the key instrument, the sampling of data sources is carried out purposively. and snowball, data collection techniques with triangulation (combined), and inductive/qualitative data analysis, and qualitative research results emphasize meaning rather than generalization". The results show that SGS has made plans but still needs improvement. The planning process for all human management activities which includes teacher procurement, teacher development,

Keywords: Teacher Management. education, Star Generation School, Bitung

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the most important asset owned by a nation. Non-human resources and abundant natural wealth do not mean much without being managed by humans properly (Siagian, 2016: 3). This is in line with Muhardi's opinion which states that "Human resources are the main asset in building a nation. The availability of abundant natural resources and the existence of capital resources and increasingly sophisticated technology will not have a value-added contribution without being supported by quality human resources" (<https://ejournal.unisba.ac.id>). That is, all resources if they are not managed by educated, skilled, disciplined, diligent, willing to work hard, and have integrity human beings will not bring benefit to the health of a nation.

Human ability in managing resources is determined by education. Long before, Theodore Schultz, an economist who won the 1979 Nobel Prize in Economics, stated that "the increase in the

welfare of the poor does not depend on land, equipment, or energy, but depends on knowledge" (Rusdiana, 2020:17). In a journal entitled Contribution of Education in Improving the Quality of the Indonesian Nation, Muhardi argues that, ...improvement of the quality of a nation actually relies on improving the quality of its human resources, and can only be achieved by one way of emphasizing the importance of education. this means that education has a very valuable and significant contribution in improving the quality of a nation (<https://e-journal.unisba.ac.id>).

Creating a quality educational institution is not an easy thing. As a system, education has many interacting factors both externally – outside educational institutions, and internally educational institutions. One of the determinants of the quality of education is management. Muhardi stated that a quality education system requires good education management (<https://e-journal.unisba.ac.id>). Mutahharah expressed the same opinion. According to him, the management and implementation of quality education will be able to prepare quality students (2021:16). This is due to the role management that provides the basis for developing and increasing the involvement of all resources in educational organizations. The overall goal of Educational management is to effectively and efficiently create and maintain an environment within Educational Institutions that promotes, supports, and maintains effective teaching and learning (Muthahharah, 2021:2).

The strategy of human management in providing quality teachers can also be understood through the research of Elton Mayo, a psychologist from Harvard who released research results with the term "hawthorne experiment". He found the results that the positive attitudes and behaviors and productivity of employees were not so much influenced by the facilities and working conditions, but by the attention paid to them by management. Furthermore, it was stated that the behavior of a worker is largely determined by and bound to the norms of the work group in which a person is a member (Siagian, 2016:39). When interpreted in the context of a school, this means that if there is no good human management, the attitude, positive behavior and productivity of teachers in carrying out their duties as educators will be low, or in other words, the quality of teachers will be low.

The educational goals to be achieved include all aspects, both faith, personality, intelligence, and skills. Education seeks to create a superior personality marked by progress in all areas of life, whether spiritual, personality, intelligence, or skills, all of which will benefit students, the environment in which they interact, and also for the progress of the nation and state.

METHODS

This research was conducted using a qualitative descriptive approach. Sugiyono explained the characteristics of qualitative research methods as follows: "Qualitative research methods are research methods based on the philosophy of postpositivism, used to examine the condition of natural objects (as opposed to experiments), where the researcher is the key instrument, the sampling of data sources is carried out purposively. and snowball, data collection techniques with triangulation (combined), and inductive/qualitative data analysis, and qualitative research results emphasize meaning rather than generalization" (2015:15)

This research was carried out at Star Generation School Bitung which includes four educational units, namely Generation Bintang Kindergarten, Generation Bintang Elementary School, Generation Bintang Junior High School, and Generation Bintang High School. The four schools are located in one location, namely in the village of Manembo-Nembo Atas, Bitung city.

"Data collection techniques are the most important step in research, because the main purpose of research is to obtain data. Without knowing the data collection technique, the researcher will not get data that meets the data standards set" (2015:308).

DISCUSSION

In this section, a researcher's study of the human management process at SGS will be presented. The presentation of the study follows the same systematics as in the previous section, which discusses the planning, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation of human management which includes activities of procurement, development, compensation, maintenance,

and separation of teachers.

1. Studies on Human Management Planning at SGS

a. Teacher Procurement Planning

The study of teacher procurement planning includes a study of the design and analysis of teacher planning, recruitment planning, selection planning, and teacher recruitment and placement planning.

Teacher Design and Analysis

Paying attention to the research data on teacher procurement planning, there are several important things that need attention: First, teacher procurement is only planned by representatives of the Foundation and does not involve principals, let alone teachers. This is evidenced by the statements of the informants who stated that none of them were involved in the planning of teacher procurement. This condition is actually understandable because SGS is a new school. SGS opened a kindergarten in 2015, then an elementary school in 2016, a junior high school in 2018, and a high school in 2021. Since it is a new school, the Foundation seems to still be accustomed to doing everything, including planning for teacher procurement.

Regardless of all the reasons that can be put forward, if the teacher procurement planning is still carried out by the Foundation itself, this will result in losses for SGS. The teacher procurement planning should be done jointly by the Foundation and the school principal. The Foundation must be involved because it is the Foundation who knows best the strategic plan of the school. In addition, the Foundation is also the one who understands the financial condition of the school the best. The procurement of teachers must of course be adjusted to the strategic plan and the financial condition of the school. As previously stated, when the Foundation made a strategic decision about opening an elementary, junior high, or high school, the number of teachers needed increased. On the other hand, although the need for teachers is quite a lot,

Meanwhile, the principal must be involved in the planning of teacher procurement, because of the consideration that the principal is the most familiar with the situation and condition of the school. The principal is also very understanding about the quality and characteristics of the existing teachers. In addition, the principal also understands the problems and dynamics that arise in the education process. This understanding of the principal will be very useful as input in teacher procurement planning, both from the quantitative aspect and from the qualitative aspect.

Second, there is a conversation among the Foundation's management about the number of teachers and the qualifications of teachers needed, but there is no comprehensive, rational, and visionary analysis about it. It is known through DHB's testimony that the teacher recruitment process is still being carried out while the new school year is already underway. This is due to the fact that the number of classes opened is greater than the number of available teachers. This means that the planning is incidental and unsystematic.

Planning conditions that are incidental and unsystematic will have a negative impact on schools. The negative impacts include: not getting the number of teachers that best suits the needs of SGS. It could be that the number of teachers is too many, which burdens the school in financing, or the number of teachers is too few so that many teachers are overburdened. This happened at SGS and it was proven by the complaints from informants about too many assignments and double jobs. Another negative impact is panic in the procurement of teachers. This panic will cause a domino effect. Panic will have an impact on the low quality of the recruitment and selection process. Because it is demanded with an urgent need, causing compromise in the recruitment and selection process. Compromise in the recruitment process in the form of lowering the standard requirements. Meanwhile, compromise in the selection process takes the form of making the selection process just a formality. The recruitment and selection process that has many compromises will have an impact on getting teachers who do not meet the expected qualifications.

Third, The foundation did not carry out job analysis properly. This is indicated by the unavailability of document products as a result of job analysis. The three documents include job descriptions, job specifications, and job performance standards. The absence of these three documents will have an

impact on the next process of human management. The absence of a job description creates confusion for teachers, more specifically home room teachers and school principals. And this has been proven through statements from several informants who said that they did not know exactly what to do when they started working. Moreover, many teachers who join SGS are fresh graduates who have no teaching experience.

Job specification explains about the profile of a job, where through understanding the job profile it can finally be known what requirements must be met by applicants in the recruitment process. Job specifications are also required during the selection process. Because by understanding what qualifications are needed in a job, the person making the selection will know what things to pay attention to in the selection process.

The third document, namely job performance standards, has an impact on teacher compensation and maintenance. The absence of performance standards causes teacher performance measures to be biased. As a result, it is difficult to provide compensation in the form of allowances because there is no measure. In addition, because there is no performance appraisal, giving a promotion or demotion will be a subjective act. Subjectivity in the organization has a negative impact on the aspect of conduciveness. Lack of a sense of fairness will lead to a decrease in work motivation and job satisfaction. This condition will then have an impact on the decline in the performance of teachers. In addition, an unhealthy culture will be formed, namely the culture of looking for faces or as long as the father is happy.

Recruitment

There are several things that researchers highlight in relation to recruitment planning, namely: first, teacher recruitment planning at SGS is incidental. From information from Foundation representatives, it is known that planning for recruitment involving Foundation management is only carried out at the beginning when starting kindergarten, and when starting junior high school. In addition, recruitment is carried out sporadically by representatives of the Foundation, in this case DHB. So recruitment planning is not an activity that is carried out regularly, scheduled and sustainable. It is only when necessary that a meeting is held, then discussed matters that are considered important. Even more Foundation representatives carry out their own planning of recruitment plans.

Second, in the statement of the Foundation's representative, it was known that nothing in the plan carried out recruitment using the referral method. In fact, if you pay attention to the information from the informants, it is known that all of the informants joined SGS because they received information from insiders whether it was direct (first person), or indirect (second person). That means that teachers who join SGS are recruited by the referral method. According to Hanggreini, the referral method is a way of collecting candidates based on recommendations from previous workers (Hanggreiny, 2012: 56). In the context of SGS, it is proven that the teachers recommended by previous teachers have quite good qualifications. However, SGS has not maximized this method. The basis for this opinion is that recruitment with this referral method is only carried out incidentally without planning. In an informal conversation, the Foundation representative asked the teachers if any of their friends had teaching skills? If there is, may be directed to apply at SGS. In the opinion of the researcher, this referral method should be maximized by: The SGS Foundation officially announces the opening of teacher job vacancies at SGS. Information about these vacancies contains the number of teachers needed, teacher qualifications required, compensation received, how to submit application documents, and who the contact person is. In addition to providing clear information about recruitment, SGS can also provide a stimulus to successful teachers, not only referencing their relationships, but if the referenced teacher candidate is finally deemed to meet the qualifications so that it is accepted by the Foundation. With this clarity and stimulus, it is hoped that the recruitment method using referrals can work well. For this reason, it is necessary to carry out careful planning in the application of recruitment with the referral method so that the results can be optimal.

Third, There were no application document requirements related to the spiritual aspects of prospective teachers. Whereas in planning the teacher qualifications desired by SGS, one of the desired criteria is listed as having good spirituality. In the existing application documents as well as information from the Foundation's representative informants and teachers, there are no application documents that provide information about the spirituality of prospective teachers such as a certificate of active worship from the Pastor, or a certificate of involvement in ecclesiastical services.

Fourth, There is no application document related to the call as a teacher even though the call plays an important role in the professionalism and resilience of the teacher in carrying out his duties. In the information from teacher informants, they found a lot of information about dissatisfaction both in terms of compensation received, workload, unclear system, and many other things. However, teachers still have the motivation to survive and carry out their duties well. All of this is due to the factor of his calling as a teacher. Therefore, the researcher believes that the application document should contain a teacher's testimony about his calling as an educator.

Fifth, from the results of the study it was found that there was no written document regarding recruitment planning. There is only an oral statement from a representative of the Foundation about what things are planned in the recruitment process. In addition, incomplete planning was also found. Taking into account the theoretical study that good planning should answer questions in the 5W + 1H pattern. For example, in the aspect of When or when. In planning there is no clarity about when this recruitment starts and how long it will take for the recruitment process. Is it only until before the school year starts, or is this recruitment open continuously until the required number of teachers has been reached. Then in the aspect of Who or who. In the planning, it is not explained in detail about who will make application advertisements through social media. Who will cooperate with schools to recruit fresh graduates? Who will cooperate with an organization like PELMAP?

Then the aspect of How or how is not yet clear. For example, what is the online recruitment procedure? If posted through a facebook account, how to respond to people who ask through the comments column? If there is an email, how to give feedback to applicants who enter incomplete application documents? Meanwhile, the how aspect is recruited through schools: how to follow up on cooperation with schools? What are the recruitment techniques? Is it giving out flyers in school wall magazines? Or how? In addition, if the recruitment is carried out through a certain organization, what is the recruitment procedure? How is the socialization? There is a lot that goes unanswered in hiring planning.

Selection

There are two things that can be highlighted in relation to selection planning, namely: selection planning procedures, and selection planning documents. Next, the researcher will describe one by one.

According to the researcher's study, the teacher selection planning procedure at SGS is incidental and needs to be improved. The reasons are: first, related to the parties involved in the preparation of the selection plan. Similar to recruitment, selection planning only involves representatives of the Foundation. The principal was not involved in planning the selection process. In fact, as the researchers described earlier, the principal is the person who understands the conditions of the school the best. In addition, the principal also quite understands what teacher qualifications are needed by the school. Without the involvement of the principal in the preparation of the selection plan, consideration will only come from representatives of the Foundation, which in the opinion of the researcher does not get comprehensive consideration. Second, the timing of the implementation of the selection planning is sudden and urgent because it is already pressed by the need for teachers. So there is no systematic and sustainable planning. In fact, this selection planning should be carried out on an ongoing basis because it considers aspects of the school's progress and dynamics internally, and external conditions. This means that the internal and external aspects of schools in 2018 will definitely not be the same as 2022. For example, planning for conducting interviews before the pandemic and during the pandemic may not be the same. Before the pandemic it can be done face-

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Studies on selection planning can also be seen through the selection planning document. From the statement of the Foundation's representatives, it was known that the selection planning was only recorded in the personal records of the Foundation's representatives, not in the form of archived documents and socialized to principals and teachers. According to researchers, this is not an ideal thing and continues to be allowed. Planning documents that are not archived properly will cause the evaluation of the planning to not be carried out properly. Meanwhile, unfiled documents caused problems in socializing to principals and teachers about the teacher selection procedure at SGS. Whereas with an understanding of the teacher selection procedure by principals and teachers,

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Second, From the information submitted by representatives of the Foundation as well as principals and teachers, the researcher believes that the implementation of the training and development program is incidental. This can be seen in the curriculum strengthening program which is a collaboration between the SGS Foundation and the Bitung City Education Office. Actually there are no plans to hold such activities. However, in a meeting with the Department, the program was finally implemented. Another program that is incidental in nature is the Mentari program. This program was implemented because the Mentari provider offered books to the Foundation and was then approved by the Foundation. Furthermore, to apply the Mentari curriculum, a curriculum strengthening program based on the Mentari book was made. Regardless of whether or not the curriculum strengthening program was implemented in collaboration with the Bitung City Education Office and the Mentari provider, it appears that the training and development program is incidental. SGS should have followed the guidelines for developing a training program proposed by Hanggreini. On the one hand, flexibility is also needed to be able to adapt to a dynamic context, however, good planning will guide the procurement and implementation of development programs that are targeted and according to needs.

Third, Unfiled training and development program planning documents will cause difficulties at the next management stage, namely the implementation and monitoring of evaluations. In the absence of properly archived planning documents, implementation will depend heavily on

Foundation representatives who plan training and development programs. Dependence can have an impact on overburden conditions that will be experienced by Foundation representatives, on the other hand it will reduce the level of participation of others in the implementation of training and development programs. In addition, the absence of good documentation and archives will have an impact on the implementation of the evaluation of training and development programs because it is not known what things must be evaluated.

Fourth, The contents of the development planning document are still incomplete and do not answer all aspects of planning that must be known. For example the Why aspect or questions about the reasons and objectives of implementing the development program. Aspects of what or what programs should be done. The who aspect is about who should carry out training and development. There is also a when aspect of when, how long, how many times the training and development program is implemented. The where aspect is about where the program is implemented. The last is the how aspect or how the training and development program procedures are carried out.

Fifth, program planning does not specifically address the development program. The training program is aimed at strengthening the ability of teachers to carry out the tasks they are currently working on, while the development program aims to prepare teachers for future tasks. The development program implemented by SGS is still focused on training programs with the aim of preparing teachers to carry out their current duties. According to the researcher, to be able to compete with other educational institutions, SGS must prepare itself to face developments in the world of education that are accelerative as a result of the industrial revolution 4.0 and the social revolution 5.0. This development requires SGS to become a digital technology-based school.

Compensation Planning

Taking into account the information from the Foundation's representatives, the researcher conveys several things that need to be considered in relation to compensation planning. First, planning on the basis of compensation needs to be adjusted again. Siagian argues that an effective compensation system must go through four things, namely: conducting a job analysis, conducting a job appraisal, conducting an external survey on the reward or compensation system, and an external survey on the price of a job (2016: 258). Hanggreini concludes in two ways: internal equity related to job evaluation, and external equity related to salary survey (2012: 140). The determination of compensation at SGS should be based on an assessment of the workload of teachers, the provisions of applicable laws, as well as salary surveys in other similar private schools.

Teacher Maintenance Planning

In terms of planning for teacher maintenance, it means that it is necessary to plan how to maintain teacher motivation, maintain teacher safety and health, and keep qualified teachers working at SGS. From the researcher's assessment of teacher maintenance planning, there are several things that need attention:

First, maintenance programs that have been implemented by SGS such as morning and afternoon devotion and fasting prayers must be continued. The planning for the morning and afternoon devotion was well executed in the form of an organized and cultured schedule. Meanwhile, prayer and fasting programs need to be optimized. Planning the prayer and fasting program should have thought about the spiritual material presented to the participants and who will deliver the spiritual material. It is hoped that good planning will produce a quality maintenance program.

Second, Another thing related to motivation is the career system. From the information obtained through representatives of the Foundation, principals, and teachers, it turns out that there is no plan for a career system. Therefore, SGS needs to design a career system that clearly includes career paths, provisions on promotions and demotions, including a performance appraisal system.

Third, SGS needs to create a harmonious and conducive work environment. Patterns of relationships and communication that respect each other must be built and developed. Planning for a compensation system as described in the previous section can also be an approach to maintain the loyalty of qualified teachers.

Teacher Separation Planning

Information received by the researcher revealed that there was no plan document regarding the termination of teacher employment. Even though there are quite a number of old teachers who have resigned at SGS. This should be the concern of the Foundation. Separation planning must begin to be considered seriously so that there are no problems related to separation. Sudden termination of teacher employment without clear planning and mechanisms can have a negative impact on the stability of learning. Each teacher has been tied to a learning schedule throughout the semester. If there are teachers who quit or are dismissed during the current academic year, this will affect the learning process. In addition to disrupting the course of the learning schedule, this condition can also affect children's psychology. Teachers are individuals who have close relationships with students. Moreover, the students here are children who often make teachers as their second parents. Disruption to the psychology of children causes a decrease in learning motivation among children. This will prompt a reaction from parents of students who question the Foundation's decision on the reasons for the termination of the teacher's employment.

In addition to having an impact on learning, child psychology, and parental resistance, termination of teacher employment if not handled properly can even result in dissatisfaction which can lead to legal proceedings. This condition can reduce the image of the school in the eyes of the community. Even the school's energy will be drained if it trips over legal problems.

2. Studies on the Implementation of Human Management at SGS

Similar to when reviewing the planning function, the study of the implementation function of human management at SGS will also follow the previous pattern, namely reviewing the implementation of procurement, development, compensation, maintenance, and separation of teachers.

Teacher Procurement

From the information obtained by the researcher, it is known that there are several things that are findings and need to be studied: First, the recruitment method has not been implemented optimally because it still relies heavily on referrals. As previously stated, all of the existing teachers joined SGS through references from people who were already familiar with SGS.

The referral method isn't wrong, but it's not the only one. In addition, if this method becomes a mainstay for a long period of time, several things will happen, namely: the shortage of people with the qualifications needed by SGS to become teachers. There are no more qualified people who can be recommended by insiders. In addition, people who are referred by insiders will usually pose a psychological dilemma in the recruitment and selection process. Subjectivity will be very dominant when giving an assessment. Moreover, if the referenced is a Foundation person, or recommended by an important person, it will make the recruitment and selection process even more difficult. As a result, the selection and recruitment process will only become a mere formality.

According to the researcher, SGS needs to optimize recruitment through advertising on social media. This should be done to expand the area of selection of prospective teachers. The researcher assumes that there are many people who have the qualifications required by SGS to become teachers but are still not connected to SGS. With advertisements on social media, the selection of prospective teachers can reach many people but is very efficient because the costs are very small.

Second, Procurement of teachers is still very dependent on representatives of the Foundation, where the involvement of principals and teachers is still lacking. In the opinion of the researcher, principals and teachers can be involved even in the roles and limitations that have been considered beforehand. Indeed, if the recruitment and procurement of teachers will be fully borne by the principal and teachers, it will increase the burden on the principal and teachers. However, if the involvement of principals and teachers is in the right portion, it will have a positive impact. The involvement of principals and teachers will further encourage the school's sense of belonging

because there is a sense of being more meaningful because they are involved in school progress. In addition to the involvement of principals and teachers, SGS should start preparing a Human Capital Department that will specifically handle the human management process at SGS.

Third, from the information of the informants, it turns out that the procurement process which includes recruitment, selection, and acceptance is not standardized properly. There are teachers who have been accepted without an interview process, there are even teachers who have worked at SGS but have not submitted their application files until now. In terms of acceptance, it turns out that there are teachers who have signed a work contract, while some have not yet signed a work contract. This condition has an impact on the unequal qualifications and competencies of teachers at SGS. There are teachers who are accepted because they have proper qualifications and competencies, some are accepted but only have modest qualifications and competencies.

This situation causes difficulties in achieving standardization and uniformity in the quality of education at SGS. Differences in teacher quality will have an impact on variations in the quality of education in each class or in each subject. For example, because third grade elementary school teachers have good quality, the quality of third grade learning is also good, so third grade students are smarter than fourth grade students who have less qualified teachers. In addition, qualified teachers will be excellent in a negative sense. Many tasks and jobs were assigned to him because it was considered that only he had the capacity to carry out these tasks. This can cause jealousy from his fellow teachers, or it can also cause overburden for the teacher because he has to carry out responsibilities beyond his abilities.

Meanwhile, teachers who have been accepted by the Foundation but have substandard abilities are also a new problem. Their inability to make a lot of problems in learning that will have an impact on parental dissatisfaction with school. This dissatisfaction if not handled properly will make many parents lose confidence in the school. Parents can transfer their child from SGS, or no longer refer SGS to others. This situation creates a dilemma for the Foundation. On the one hand, the Foundation is faced with the need to address the problem of learning quality by replacing less qualified teachers with qualified teachers. But if the Foundation does that, there will be an excess of teachers at SGS which will have an impact on increasing the budget for teacher compensation. Another option for the Foundation is to terminate the employment relationship with teachers. However, this condition can also cause new problems because it is not easy to suddenly terminate the employment relationship. Teachers who are terminated suddenly can file an objection or protest. Especially if the teacher whose quality is below the standard turns out to have close relationships with important people at SGS.

Paying attention to this study, the researcher sees the importance for SGS to compile a manual book on teacher procurement starting from the process of recruitment, selection, acceptance, and placement of teachers.

Teacher Development

There are several things that are of concern to researchers in connection with the implementation of teacher development programs, namely:

First, need to evaluate existing training programs. The programs that have been implemented include: English club, In House Training, I Walk With God character curriculum training, Learning Management System training from Ruang Guru, Mentari curriculum training, Government curriculum training by the Bitung City Education Office. From the information that the researchers got, the English language training program called the English Club did not run well. The program had no measurable goals, had no planned curriculum, was implemented inconsistently, and finally ended in just two months. This training program needs to be maintained and even better maximized because one of the highlights at SGS is bilingual learning which tends to be active English with the motto English First.

Furthermore, the I Walk With God character curriculum training program needs to be held again. From information from the Foundation and teachers, it is known that character curriculum

training is only carried out twice, namely at the beginning of the 2016-2017 and 2017-2018 school years. This program needs to be re-implemented because it is related to other advantages of SGS. In addition to being bilingual, SGS is a school that defines character strengthening as one of the best. According to the informant, the character curriculum training is the result of the collaboration between SGS and the Tunas Bangsa Foundation. To be applicable, Tunas Bangsa Foundation carries out a training package containing the I Walk With God student and teacher book, a guide to the implementation of character assessment, as well as mentoring for teachers in using the I Walk With God book and character assessment books.

Furthermore, the Learning Management System from Ruang Guru and the Mentari curriculum need to be reviewed by the SGS Foundation. If it is still relevant to the needs, it is recommended that the implementation of the training should be carried out before the start of the new school year. This is intended so that teachers are ready in advance to apply this curriculum in learning. It was obtained information that although Ruang Guru had conducted training, many teachers did not use learning based on the learning management system from the teacher's room. Likewise with the Mentari curriculum, there are still many teachers who have difficulty applying this curriculum.

Second, From the results of interviews with informants from both the Foundation and teachers, it is known that many teachers at SGS are fresh graduates who still lack teaching experience. Meanwhile, until now the teacher training program that touches on classroom mastery and management skills has not been implemented. From the information from the informants who were fresh graduates, they felt overwhelmed in dealing with students. Many are stressed by this situation that prevents them from carrying out high-performance tasks. They have a bachelor's degree in education, but practical skills in classroom control and management need to be trained so that they are ready to carry out their duties, let alone become home room teachers.

Third, still related to the second matter, it is necessary to carry out training programs and develop leadership and management skills. Being a teacher, let alone being a school principal, is required to have good leadership and management skills. Without these two soft skills, teachers will have difficulty carrying out their duties as educators. With leadership skills, teachers have the authority to carry out their roles as educators, instructors, trainers, assessors as mandated by law. Meanwhile, with good management skills, teachers can manage their learning and teacher tasks optimally.

Fourth, With the industrial revolution 4.0, it has even entered the 5.0 social revolution, requiring teachers to have mastery of skills in the field of information technology. Many experts state that as a result of the industrial revolution 4.0 and even the 5.0 social revolution, there has been disruption in the education sector. A technology-based learning approach has become a necessity in today's learning implementation. If the teacher does not have the provision of mastery of information technology, the teacher will have difficulty carrying out his duties as a teacher.

Compensation

Almost all the teachers interviewed were dissatisfied with the compensation received. This condition must be taken seriously by the Foundation because it will have an effect on several things, including: decreased motivation and job satisfaction which has an impact on the performance of teachers; the creation of a gap between the teacher community and the Foundation which results in the creation of an environment that is not conducive due to a less harmonious and suspicious relationship; the high desire of the teachers to end their employment relationship, so that SGS could lose its best teachers because they moved to other schools that offered more profitable salaries and benefits.

Maintenance

There are several things that are of concern to researchers in connection with maintenance activities, namely:

First, SGS must design and implement a clear career system for teachers at SGS. This career

system will encourage teachers to work at SGS for a long period of time even into retirement. With the insight into thinking for long-term work, it creates psychological stability for teachers to work diligently. In addition, with a clear career system, teachers will not hesitate to bring out their best abilities because they feel that everything they will do will not be ignored by the Foundation, even if they will get Foundation awards through promotion policies. Meanwhile, with a clear career system, it indirectly warns teachers who are less professional because there is demotion for those who do not work well.

Second, SGS has held a spirituality program as a way of nurturing teachers. As explained in the previous section, humans must be seen not only as one of the same resources as other resources, but humans are human beings who have moral and spiritual aspects. Human needs are not only in the physical aspect, but also in the spiritual aspect. From interviews with teachers, a unique and anomaly fact was obtained. Almost all teachers are not satisfied with the compensation. However, only one has low work motivation, other than that it is moderate or even high. Even the lowly motivated teacher is still working professionally. According to the researcher, this is caused by the spiritual aspect, namely the awareness that educating children is a call from God that he must do as a form of his faith and love for God. Therefore, even though the compensation has not been satisfactory, there are various challenges and struggles related to their duties and responsibilities, the teachers still carry out their profession well. Therefore, it is hoped that the spiritual program that has been implemented so far will be maintained and even maximized its implementation so that it is more useful.

Third, some teachers feel overwhelmed by the workload they have to carry. Therefore, the implementation of teacher counseling needs to be done to enable teachers to deal with stress at work.

Teacher Separation

As previously stated, many teachers have resigned from SGS. Some who resign due to differences of opinion between teachers and the Foundation. After resigning, the teachers felt they were being treated unfairly by the Foundation. Meanwhile, the Foundation also feels that the teacher who has resigned has not been treated well. Therefore, the provision of a teacher separation system is a non-negotiable necessity.

Study on Monitoring & Evaluation

Of the three human management functions at SGS, monitoring and evaluation are the least concerned. Actually, monitoring is carried out directly by representatives of the Foundation. However, the monitoring carried out so far is not related to human management. The focus of monitoring by representatives of the Foundation on the implementation of learning and school programs. From the Foundation's information, it was obtained information that the supervision of teacher procurement activities, teacher development, compensation for teachers, teacher maintenance, and teacher separation took place naturally and was not a priority. In fact, strengthening human management through the implementation of managerial functions on operational functions will have a positive effect on the quality of education at SGS. It has been described previously that the quality of education in schools is highly dependent on the quality of teachers. If the SGS teachers are managed properly, the teacher's performance will increase which in turn can encourage the increase in the quality of education at SGS. Monitoring is a way of management to ensure that what is planned goes as it should. Monitoring is also useful so that appropriate steps can be taken if the implementation of the plan needs adjustments and adaptations due to the situation and conditions. In other words, monitoring will make the implementation of the plan controlled but still flexible under dynamic conditions. Monitoring is a way of management to ensure that what is planned goes as it should. Monitoring is also useful so that appropriate steps can be taken if the implementation of the plan needs adjustments and adaptations due to the situation and conditions. In other words, monitoring will make the implementation of the plan controlled but still flexible under dynamic conditions. Monitoring is a way of management to ensure that what is planned goes as it should. Monitoring is also useful so that appropriate steps can be taken if the implementation of the plan

needs adjustments and adaptations due to the situation and conditions. In other words, monitoring will make the implementation of the plan controlled but still flexible under dynamic conditions.

Meanwhile, the evaluation function of human management at SGS is also not implemented. This is evidenced by the fact that there are no guidelines or evaluation documents for human management activities. In fact, with a correct and ongoing evaluation of human management activities, this will affect the quality of teachers' human capital at SGS. For example, if there is a good evaluation of the recruitment system, the SGS Foundation will realize that the recruitment of teachers at SGS through social media has not yet achieved satisfactory results. This is evidenced by the fact that none of the teachers at SGS have been caught through social media.

A good school is if it carries out a planned, systematic, and sustainable monitoring and evaluation function. The managerial function of management which includes planning, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation is a cycle that must be carried out in a disciplined and continuous manner. If one function is neglected, it will interfere with other functions. Inadequate planning will have an impact on the low quality of the implementation function. Organizations will find it difficult to implement what was not planned. Even if there are things that are done, they are not implementation, but sudden and sporadic activities whose impact on the achievement of organizational goals cannot be measured. Without planning, monitoring and evaluation cannot be carried out properly. The supervisory function cannot work because it does not know what is the correct standard. The same applies to the evaluation aspect. Something that can only be judged if something is planned. On the other hand, good planning requires evaluation. The results of the evaluation will be useful data in making plans.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion of the research results that have been presented in chapter four, it can be concluded:

1. SGS has done some planning but still needs improvement. The planning process for all human management activities which include teacher procurement, teacher development, teacher compensation, teacher maintenance, and teacher separation has not gone well. This conclusion was based on several reasons: first, planning was only carried out by representatives of the Foundation without involving the principal or teachers; second, planning does not go through the results of an analysis based on an evaluation of the existing situation and conditions; third, the content of the plan is incomplete because it does not provide a comprehensive answer to the 5W + 1H pattern; fourth, planning does not cover all human management activities. Some activities such as job analysis design, development programs, career systems, teacher separation procedures have gone unnoticed, so there is no planning at all; fifth, planning results are not well documented. Some planning documents are only in the form of notes stored on the smartphones of Foundation representatives.

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